

Mwanagori Cave

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Mwanagori Cave is a limestone karst cavern that lies on the road between Jambiani and Makunduchi, close to Shuungi. The cave is inset within a limestone cliff and is surrounded by a small grove that has been deemed sacred. The entrance to the cave is narrow and require sure-footedness, and is partially screened by rows of boulders. The ritual significance of this cave and the antiquity of human use is evidenced by the the deep wearing and polishing of the stones leading into the cave. Within the cave, in a dark recess lies a pool of fresh water, near which a spirit or Shetani is supposed to reside. The word "Shetani" is etymologically linked with the Arabic word "Shaitan" ("satan/demon"). This places Mwanagori squarely in the Zanzibari pattern in which caves with a pool/spring of fresh water are considered sacred due to the presence/residence of spirits known as Shetani. In Zanzibari practice, the shetani are venerated even though the population of the island is overwhelmingly Muslim. The syncretic nature of Swahili Islam allows for the practice of pre-/non-Islamic religious traditions by local Muslims. Mwanagori Cave is cared for by the local community, and has a healer known as an mganga (pl. waganga) in charge of the rites performed there. The rites and rituals performed by the mganga at Mwanagori remain secret, just as they are at other caves on Zanzibar. However, evidence for the practice of rituals at Mwanagori exists in the form of offerings left for the Shetani. These offerings often take the form of food, drink, and incense. There is also a tradition of tying strips of cloth (especially white and red) to the trees near the cave. This practice is akin to what takes place at the nearby Kuumbi Cave, which is also managed by an mganga and is visited by the pious among the local community, who arrive to leave offerings of food, incense, and cloth. The rituals and rites conducted in caves like Mwanagori are considered part of the intangible heritage of Zanzibar, but they are increasingly under threat from the tourism industry. Tour operators regularly remove offerings from caves and prevent the waganga and the local community from performing their rituals for fear that this performance of "witchcraft" will drive away tourists. No archaeological research has been conducted at Mwanagori as of December 2023. This cave is important to the local communities of the nearby settlements of Makunduchi, Jambiani, and Shuungi. The disruption caused to these communities by the expansion of the tourist industry could harm cave shrines like Mwanagori.

Date Range: 0 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Unguja - Southeast

Region tags: Africa, Eastern Africa, Tanzania, Zanzibar, Unguja

Mwanagori Cave is sacred to the people who live in the southeast of Unguja (Zanzibar Island) - specifically, in the settlements of Jambiani, Makunduchi, and Shuungi.

Status of Participants:

✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: There are no print sources dealing with Mwanagori Cave as of December 2023

Notes: There are no print sources dealing with Mwanagori Cave as of December 2023

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: There are no online sources dealing with Mwanagori Cave as of December 2023

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– No

Notes: Excavations are planned for 2025. No excavations have taken place as of December 2023. The sacred nature of the space means that little digging has taken place at the site.

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Tree, grove, or forest

– Cave

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Notes: The settlements of Jambiani, Makunduchi, and Shuungi, are within a few km of the cave.

Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Notes: A tarred road connects Jambiani with Makunduchi. A dirt trail leads off from this main road to the limestone cliffs at which Mwanagori is located.

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– Yes

Notes: A tarred road connects Jambiani with Makunduchi. A dirt trail leads off from this main road to the limestone cliffs at which Mwanagori is located.

Is there an established route of travel connecting it to a wider transportation network:

– Yes

Notes: A tarred road connects Jambiani with Makunduchi. A dirt trail leads off from this main road to the limestone cliffs at which Mwanagori is located.

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

A single structure

– No

One single feature

– Purposefully placed plants

Notes: There is a small scared grove surrounding the cave. The cave is also located in a limestone cliff face and is surrounded by large boulders.

A group of structures:

– No

A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: There is a small scared grove surrounding the cave. The cave is also located in a limestone cliff face and is surrounded by large boulders.

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

–Other [specify]: Both communal and individual worship takes place at the cave.

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– No

Notes: But the stones on the floor of the cave have been worn and polished smooth by likely centuries of feet rubbing against them.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Notes: The cave has no modifications visible to the eye.

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: The cave is sacred to a spirit known as a shetani

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Notes: The cave is sacred to a spirit known as a shetani. This shetani could be an ancestral spirit, but

likely is simply a spirit associated with the spring within the cave.

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Notes: The cave is sacred to a spirit known as a shetani. This shetani could be an ancestral spirit, but likely is simply a spirit associated with the spring within the cave.

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– No

Notes: The cave and its freshwater spring/pool are natural structures and have been minimally modified by humans.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– No

Notes: There are no structures associated with the cave and its freshwater spring/pool. The setting is entirely natural.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– I don't know

Notes: While other nearby caves have their own stories of discovery, there is no such story has thus far been associated with Mwanagori Cave.

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Notes: The cave and its associated spring/pool of freshwater are natural features. However, it is possible that their discovery by humans was associated with the birth of a supernatural or human being.

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– I don't know

Notes: The cave and its associated spring/pool of freshwater are natural features. However, it is possible that their discovery by humans was associated with a (supernatural) event of some kind.

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Notes: The cave and its spring/pool of freshwater are natural features. However, offerings may be made by financial contributions from the nearby communities of Jambiani, Makunduchi, and Shuungi.

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

- Other [specify]: The cave and its associated spring/pool of freshwater are natural features. However, it is possible that their status as ritual places is linked to events of thanksgiving to a god/gods, expectation of a favor in return, or mere expressions of devotion with no expectation of favor in return. The spirit currently venerated in the cave is considered relatively benign but it must be propitiated.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

- No

Notes: No sacred texts/scriptures are stored/associated with the cave. However, waganga often use books associated with Islamic magical practice, and it is possible that they use them in their rituals at Mwanagori Cave.

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

- No

Notes: The cave and the spring/pool of freshwater which are considered sacred are natural features.

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

- No

Notes: The cave could be considered monumental, but it is not as large as some other nearby sacred caves like Kuumbi.

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

- Yes

↳ Earth

- Yes

Notes: Earth forms the floor of the pathway leading to the cave and the floor of the cave.

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

- Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Sand
– Yes

Notes: Beach sand partly forms the floor of the pathway leading to the cave and the floor of the cave.

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Clay
– No

↳ Plaster
– No

↳ Wood
– Yes

Notes: The wood consists of a small sacred grove that surrounds the cave.

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Grass
– Yes

Notes: Some grass grows on the pathway to the cave

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– Yes

↳ Stone
– Yes

Notes: The cave is composed of limestone.

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: There is a water feature (a spring/pool of freshwater) at the back of the cave

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– No

Notes: But the stones on the floor of the cave have been worn smooth and polished by centuries (?) of feet rubbing against them.

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Notes: There is no iconography in the cave.

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– I don't know

Notes: There may be burials within the cave or under its floor, like at Kuumbi Cave. Only archaeological investigations will be able to properly answer this question.

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Notes: The spirit venerated at the shrine is known as a Shetani. It may be linked to ancestors, but I was not informed so.

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Notes: To the best of my knowledge, the sacred caves of Zanzibar are not associated with the treatment of corpses.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– I don't know

Notes: This depends on whether burials are present in the cave. As no archaeological investigations have taken place in the cave as of December 2023, this question remains unanswerable.

Are grave goods present:

– I don't know

Notes: This depends on whether burials are present in the cave. As no archaeological investigations have taken place in the cave as of December 2023, this question remains unanswerable.

Are formal burials present:

– I don't know

Notes: There may be burials within the cave or under its floor, like at Kuumbi Cave. Only archaeological investigations will be able to properly answer this question.

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Notes: A spirit known as a shetani is present. This is not a high god. The locals are overwhelmingly Muslim, and their worship of the high god Allah takes place at mosques.

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Notes: A spirit known as a shetani is present. This is not a high god. The locals are overwhelmingly

Muslim, and their worship of the high god Allah takes place at mosques. The spirit may communicate with the mganga and others, but this remains unknown.

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Notes: A spirit known as a shetani is present. This may be linked to ancestors, but is likely linked to sacred character of caves with freshwater in Zanzibari tradition.

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Notes: A spirit known as a shetani is present. This may be linked to ancestors or may be a human spirit, but is likely linked to sacred character of caves with freshwater in Zanzibari tradition.

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be seen:

– I don't know

Notes: A spirit known as a shetani is present. This may be linked to ancestors, but is likely linked to sacred character of caves with freshwater in Zanzibari tradition. Whether the spirit can be seen or felt by religious practitioners/visitors remains unknown.

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:

– I don't know

Notes: A spirit known as a shetani is present. This may be linked to ancestors, but is likely linked to sacred character of caves with freshwater in Zanzibari tradition. Whether the spirit can be seen or felt by religious practitioners/visitors remains unknown.

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– I don't know

Notes: A spirit known as a shetani is present. This may be linked to ancestors, but is likely linked to sacred character of caves with freshwater in Zanzibari tradition. Whether the spirit communicates with religious practitioners/visitors remains unknown.

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Notes: A spirit known as a shetani is present. This may be linked to ancestors, but is likely linked to sacred character of caves with freshwater in Zanzibari tradition. The shetani is likely not a human-divine hybrid.

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Notes: A spirit known as a shetani is present. This may be linked to ancestors, but is likely linked to sacred character of caves with freshwater in Zanzibari tradition. The shetani is likely not a human-divine hybrid, but may communicate with the mganga and others who visit the cave.

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Notes: There is no cult statue depicting the shetani.

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– I don't know

Notes: A spirit known as a shetani is present. This may be linked to ancestors, but is likely linked to sacred character of caves with freshwater in Zanzibari tradition. The shetani likely does not supernaturally monitor the living.

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– I don't know

Notes: It is possible that the waganga and others who visit the cave and perform rites there communicate with the shetani, but this remains uncertain.

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– No

Notes: Rituals tend to be performed by small groups of people or individual mganga.

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: Rituals are performed by small groups of people or individual mganga.

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: No large-scale rituals take place

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: The frequency of rituals of any kind remains unknown, especially as some seem to perform them as needed.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– No

Notes: These practices take place on the fringes of Swahili Islam. As such, they represent the heterodoxy and heteropraxy inherent in the syncretized nature of Islam in East Africa.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– No

Notes: These practices take place on the fringes of Swahili Islam. As such, they represent the heterodoxy and heteropraxy inherent in the syncretized nature of Islam in East Africa.

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– I don't know

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– I don't know

Notes: Intoxicants could be used, but this is unknown.

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal sacrifices:

– I don't know

Notes: Animal sacrifices (especially of chickens) are performed at other sacred caves on Zanzibar, so it is possible that they are performed at Mwanagori as well.

↳ Are there human sacrifices:

– No

Notes: To my knowledge, no human sacrifices are associated with any of the sacred caves of Zanzibar.

↳ Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:

– I don't know

Notes: There are likely no sacrificed humans.

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– I don't know

Notes: To the best of my knowledge, no self-sacrifices are present at any of the sacred caves of Zanzibar.

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– Yes

Notes: Material offerings are mandatory in the performance of rituals at the cave. They consist of food, drink, cloth, and incense.

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– I don't know

Notes: The answer to this question depends on what value is placed on food, drink, cloth, and incense by the locals. Some items, like cloth, are definitely not everyday purchases for most people.

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

Notes: The offerings consist of everyday objects of food, drink, cloth, and incense.

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– I don't know

Notes: Only archaeological investigation will answer this question. However, most offerings seem to have been left on the surface, on soil or rocks.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: None

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Notes: Attendance is not mandatory. In fact, some rituals are performed in secret by the mganga

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

Is it required:

– I don't know

Notes: The cave is swept and kept clear of vegetation and debris. Whether this is done out of respect for the sacred nature of the space or if it is mandatory remains unknown.

Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Yes

Notes: The cave is swept and kept clear of vegetation and debris. Whether this is done out of respect for the sacred nature of the space or if it is mandatory remains unknown.

Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– No

Notes: As the cave and its associated pool/spring are natural features, no repairs or constructions are performed.

Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– No

Notes: Worshippers and even the mganga are not specialists or permanent staff. They attend to the cave and its rituals in addition to their daily occupations.

Other

– Other [specify]: None

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– I don't know

Notes: While waganga perform divination rituals in their homes, it is unknown whether they perform these at the cave.

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– I don't know

Notes: While waganga perform healing rituals in their homes, it is unknown whether they perform these at the cave.

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– No

↳ Present part time

– Yes

Notes: The waganga are present part-time in the cave.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: While the waganga are currently exclusively male, it is possible that women were ritual specialists in charge of the cave in the past.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Yes

Notes: The waganga are all from the local Swahili-speaking communities.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– Yes

Notes: Being an mganga places one in a separate social class.

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– I don't know

Notes: The waganga generally are tied to a local community and therefore tend not to be mobile. So they may be dedicated to the cave for life simply by virtue of not moving.

Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Notes: The waganga live in the local community.

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– I don't know

Notes: Training of future waganga could take place at this cave. It takes place at the homes of waganga.

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– No

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

Public food distribution and/or storage:

– No

- ↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):
 - No
- ↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):
 - No
- ↳ Function for water management:
 - No
- ↳ Part of the transportation network:
 - No
- ↳ Other
 - Other [specify]: Religious services are performed for the local community.

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– I don't know

Notes: The waganga use books of Islamic magic. I do not know whether any of them specifically are tied to this place.